

Bacterial Aetiologic Profile and Antibiotic Response Patterns of Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (LRTI) among HIV/AIDS Patients on Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy (HAART) in Uyo, South-south Nigeria

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Summary

Highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) decreases HIV viral load which in turn increases CD4 counts and that is expected to reduce the risk of opportunistic infections like lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI). The present study therefore assessed the bacterial aetiologic profile and their antibiotic response patterns of lower respiratory tract infection (LRTI) among HIV patients on highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) in Uyo, Nigeria. This study included 61 people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) on HAART. Hospital records, standardized questionnaires

were administered and sputum specimen free from salivary contamination was collected from the participants. The sputum samples were subjected to laboratory analysis of the sputum samples including macroscopy, microscopy, culture and biochemical analysis on isolates were done. Antibiotic susceptibility testing on isolates using conventional bacteriologic methods was also performed. According to our results, of the 61 samples, 24 (39.3%) yielded bacterial growth comprising of *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Rothia kristinae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Proteus* spp. Prevalence of LRTI was statistically associated ($p < 0.05$) with CD4 counts, viral load and age, but not statistically associated ($p > 0.05$) with sex, occupation, marital status and educational level of patient. In both Gram positive and Gram negative isolates, imipenem showed high sensitivity while trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole showed high level of resistance. In conclusion, the present study confirms increased CD4 count and reduced viral load to be the best intervention for the prevention of opportunistic infections like LRTI in PLWHA on HAART.

Key words

lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs), antiretroviral therapy (ART), people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA), CD4, Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS)

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Introduction

HIV is a major contributor to the global burden of disease.¹ Despite the gains made in fighting Human Immunodeficiency Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS), the epidemic still remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa due to co-infection with opportunistic infections.² As at the end of 2019, about 38 million people around the world were thought to be living with HIV, 25.6 million of these were in sub-Saharan Africa.³ Nigeria has the second highest number of people living with HIV/AIDS in the world after South Africa.³ In 2021, a survey conducted in Uyo by Akwa Ibom AIDS Indicator Survey (AKAIS) had HIV prevalence to be 4.8% and recorded 13,000 new cases of HIV infections annually in Akwa Ibom.⁴ The immune system, through white blood cells helps the body fight infections and other diseases.⁵ HIV eliminates the white blood cell lymphocyte subpop-

ulations of CD4 T-cells and B-cells⁶ thereby making the body lose its ability to defend itself against common pathogens. When HIV infection is untreated, majority of patients experience immune system deficits that lead to deadly opportunistic infections, like lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs).^{7,8} However, initiation of antiretroviral therapy (ART) significantly reduces the incidence of opportunistic infections including LRTIs among PLWHA,⁹ by increasing the CD4 counts to a normal range.¹⁰ Clinicians use CD4 cells to monitor the effectiveness of the antiretroviral treatment (ART),¹¹ and a decline in CD4 cells can lead to opportunistic infections, which in turn leads to mortality.¹² The respiratory system is the most frequently affected organ system by HIV infection.¹³ LRTI are 25-fold more common in people with AIDS than in the general population, occurring in about 90 cases per 1,000 person-years.¹⁴ HIV infection causes alteration in several lines of host defenses in the respiratory tract that contribute to an increased risk for pulmonary in-

fection.¹⁵ These alterations include abnormalities in mucociliary function and soluble defense molecules, such as defensins within respiratory secretions. Within the lung parenchyma, innate and adaptive immune responses to pathogens may be impaired.¹⁶ For example, alveolar macrophages from HIV infected individuals have been shown to be deficient in pathogen recognition. Besides, HIV also results in chronic stimulation and activation of inflammatory cells within the alveolar space.¹⁷ The lower respiratory tract infections are the most frequent respiratory diseases among HIV infected patients and are frequently the first clinical manifestations of the HIV infections.¹⁸ Diverse types of organisms including Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria are responsible for LRTIs in people living with HIV (PLWHA) which include *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Hemophilus influenzae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *M. tuberculosis* and *Acinetobacter spp.*¹⁹ Diagnosing LRTI could be done using GeneXpert MTB/RIF²⁰ or sputum microscopy, culture and sensitivity (MCS).²¹ The right diagnosis or identification of pathogens causing LRTI and their antimicrobial susceptibility tests provide great guidance to clinicians for better management of the HIV patient. There is currently no study from this region that assessed LRTI prevalence in PLWHA on HAART. Therefore, this study bridged that gap by analyzing sputum samples from HIV patients on HAART with the view to identify LRTI causing organisms present, and test for their susceptibility and resistance pattern to available antibiotics in use in the hospital and the region.

Materials and Methods

Study Size, Population and Area

A total of 61 people living with HIV/AIDS on antiretroviral therapy (ART) attending HIV clinics at University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH) and St Luke Hospital Anua (SLHA), within Uyo metropolis from the period of November to December, 2021, were recruited using simple random sampling technique (balloting). Uyo is the capital of Akwa Ibom State, South-Southern part of Nigeria. Uyo lies between latitude 5.50N and 6.00N and longitude 6.00E and 6.50E of Greenwich Meridian.

Inclusion Criteria

Eligible individuals for this study were consenting HIV infected patients on antiretroviral therapy (ART) that provided on-request sputum samples for suspected lower respiratory tract infection.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria included HIV negative patients, HIV positive patients not on ART and those on antibiotic usage within 1 week prior to clinic visit.

Method of Data Collection

The 61 selected participants were informed of the study's objectives, methods, and relevance. Hospital records and standardized questionnaires presented by interviewers were used to collect data. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents by trained health-care providers and were appropriately completed with close monitoring/guidance. Each responder in the study group had their most recent CD4 counts (within the previous six months) taken from their folders and entered into the questionnaires.

Collection and Laboratory Analysis of Samples

An early morning or spot sputum specimen of required quality was aseptically collected from each participant using sterile containers.²² These samples were promptly transported and analyzed in the laboratory within 4 hours. The samples were aseptically inoculated on Sheep blood agar (SBA), Mac Conkey agar and chocolate agar plates by direct inoculation using a sterile loop. The inoculated SBA plates were then incubated aerobically at 35°C for 24hours, while the chocolate agar plates were incubated in an anaerobic jar at 37°C also for 24hours. After incubation, the plates were properly identified following morphological characteristics; growth of the pathogens, sizes and shapes of colonies, odour, pigmentation, haemolysis and swarming movement, Gram reaction and biochemical tests included citrate, oxidase, indole, coagulase, catalase, methyl red and Voges-Proskauer test.²³ *Streptococcus sp* was properly identified using automated method with the VITEK 2 system (BioMérieux, France) (figure 1).

Antibiotic Sensitivity Screening

Mueller-Hinton agar plates were inoculated with 0.5 McFarland preparation of the inoculum using the spread plate technique. Standard antibiotic discs were placed on the surface of the inoculated agar plates using sterile forceps. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After 24 hours, the plates were observed for the zones of inhibition and interpreted as 'Resistant', 'Intermediate/Moderately susceptible', or 'Susceptible' according to the standard chart using the Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute guidelines.²⁴

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the medical re-

search and ethics committee of UUTH, Uyo and letter of introduction was sent to St. Luke's Hospital, Anua, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Informed consent form was issued to the eligible subjects and only subjects that gave informed consent were included in the study.

Statistical Analysis

All the gathered data from the participants were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS Statistics software package (version 22.0). Descriptive statistics was used for data summarization and presentation. Data obtained was analyzed statistically using Chi-square test. P values <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Socio-demographic Profile of Participants

In the 61 sputum samples submitted, 24 (39.3%) were culture positive while 37 (60.7%) were culture negative. Bacterial occurrence was higher in females (18: 40%) than in males (6: 37.5%) (Table 1). The highest bacterial occurrence was among the age range 31-45 years with 13 (59.1%), and unemployed participants were also observed to have the highest bacterial occurrence of 11 (55%). Participants that were single had the highest culture positivity rate of 42.9%, while those married had 31.6% rate (Table 1). Those with primary level of education had the highest prevalence (5: 45.5%), while those with secondary education had the lowest (7: 33.3%) (Table 1). Prevalence of LRTI was

statistically not associated ($p > 0.05$) with sex, occupation, marital status and educational level of patient, but was statistically associated ($p < 0.05$) with age of patient (Table 1).

Distribution of Bacterial Isolates from Sputum Samples

Out of the 61 samples processed, a total of 24 (39.3%) (Figure 2) samples yielded clinically significant pathogens comprising of 4 different Gram-positive organisms [*Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Rothia kristinae* (formerly *Kocuria kristinae*), *Staphylococcus aureus*] and 3 Gram-negative organisms (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus spp*). St. Luke Hospital, Anua (SLHA) had the highest number of bacterial isolates with 79.2% occurrence rate, while University of Uyo Teaching Hospital (UUTH) had 20.8% occurrence rate (Table 2).

Distribution of Bacterial growth according to CD4 count and Viral Load

Among different CD4 cell count categories, rate of LRTI was higher among those with CD4 cell of 201-300 cells/mm³ (9, 64.3%), while those with CD4 cells above 301-400 cells/mm³ (2: 16.7%) had the lowest LRTI rate (Table 3). Of the total cases on ART, those with viral load above 1000 copies/ml (23, 45.1%) had the highest LRTI prevalence rate compared with those that had viral load below 1000 copies/ml (1: 10%) (Table 3). Prevalence of LRTI was statistically associated ($p < 0.05$) with CD4 counts and viral load of patient (Table 3).

Figure 1 The Vitek 2 Compact 60 (BioMérieux, France) system in University of Uyo teaching hospital.

Table 1 Occurrence of Bacterial Isolates according to their Socio-demographic Characteristics.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics		No of Samples	Growth (%)	No growth (%)	X ²	p-value
Sex	Male	16	6 (37.5)	10 (62.5)	0.031	0.86
	Female	45	18 (40)	27 (60)		
Age (yrs)	≤15	4	0 (0)	4 (100)	8.155	0.043
	16-30	29	8 (27.6)	21 (72.4)		
	31-45	22	13 (59.1)	9 (40.9)		
	≥ 46	6	3 (50)	3 (50)		
Occupation	Self employed	16	7 (43.8)	9 (56.2)	6.099	0.192
	Trader	7	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)		
	Student	12	2 (16.7)	10 (83.3)		
	Civil Servant	6	1 (16.7)	5 (83.3)		
	Unemployed	20	11 (55)	9 (45)		
Marital status	Single	42	18 (42.9)	24 (57.1)	0.697	0.404
	Married	19	6 (31.6)	13 (68.4)		
Educational Levels	None	7	3 (42.9)	4 (57.1)	0.549	0.908
	Primary	11	5 (45.5)	6 (54.5)		
	Secondary	21	7 (33.3)	14 (66.7)		
	Tertiary	22	9 (40.9)	13 (59.1)		
Total		61	24 (39.3)	37 (60.7)		

*Significance at $p = 0.05$ | Source: Field data, 2021

Figure 2

Distribution of Bacterial Isolates.

Table 2 Distribution of Bacterial Isolates Identified from Sputum Specimen of Patient with suspected LRTI at University of Uyo Teaching Hospital and SLHA.

Isolate	Gram reactions	Growth (%)	UUTH (%)	SLHA (%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	6 (25)	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)
<i>Proteus spp</i>	-ve	2 (8.3)	0 (0)	2 (100)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-ve	3 (12.5)	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)
<i>Rothia kristinae</i>	+ve	1 (4.2)	0 (0)	1 (100)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-ve	4 (16.7)	1 (2.3)	3 (75)
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	+ve	3 (12.5)	0 (0)	3 (100)
<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	+ve	5 (20.8)	1 (20)	4 (80)
Total		24	5 (20.8)	19 (79.2)

Source: Field data, 2021
Abbreviations: UUTH= University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, SLHA = St. Luke Hospital, Anua, +ve = Positive, -ve = Negative

Table 3 Distribution of Bacterial Isolates according to Immunologic staging (CD4 count) and Viral Load.

Variables	No of Samples	Growth	No Growth	X ²	p-value
CD4 (cells/mm³)					
<200	24	11 (45.8)	13 (54.2)	9.594	0.048
201-300	14	9 (64.3)	5 (35.7)		
301-400	12	2 (16.7)	10 (58.3)		
401-500	7	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)		
>500	4	0 (0)	4 (100)		
Viral Load (copies/ml)					
Suppressed <1000	11	2 (18.2)	9 (81.8)	4.316	0.038
Unsuppressed ≥1000	50	22 (44)	28 (56)		
Total	61	24	37		

Source: Field data, 2021

Antibiotics Susceptibility Pattern of Bacterial Isolates

Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria were most sensitive to imipenem, 93.3% and 77.8% respectively. Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (40%) and ceftriax-

one (51.7%) were the most resisted antibiotics by Gram positive bacteria (Table 4), while gentamicin (44.4%), azithromycin (33.3%) and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (33.3%) were the most resisted antibiotics by Gram positive bacteria (Table 5).

Table 4 Antibiotic Susceptibility Patterns of Gram positive Isolates from Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (LRTI).

Antibiotics (μ g)	Sensitive	Intermediate	Resistant
CN (10)	9 (60)	4 (26.7)	2 (13.3)
AMC (10)	7 (46.7)	6 (40)	2 (13.3)
CRO (30)	6 (40)	5 (33.3)	4 (26.7)
IMI (10)	14 (93.3)	1 (6.7)	0 (0)
SXT (25)	7 (46.7)	2 (13.3)	6 (40)
E (15)	6 (40)	8 (53.3)	1 (6.7)
DA (2)	8 (53.3)	5 (33.3)	2 (13.3)

Source: Field data, 2021
Abbreviations: AMC = amoxicillin clavulanic acid, CN = gentamicin, IMI = imipenem, DA = clindamycin, SXT = Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, E = erythromycin, CRO = ceftriaxone, S = Sensitivity, I = Intermediate, R = Resistance

Table 5 Antibiotic Susceptibility Patterns of Gram negative Isolates from Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (LRTI).

Antibiotics (μ g)	Sensitive	Intermediate	Resistant
CN (10)	4 (44.4)	1 (11.1)	4 (44.4)
AMC (10)	6 (66.7)	2 (22.2)	1 (11.1)
CAZ (30)	5 (55.6)	3 (33.3)	1 (11.1)
IMI (10)	7 (77.8)	1 (11.1)	1 (11.1)
SXT (25)	5 (55.6)	1 (11.1)	3 (33.3)
CRO (30)	6 (66.7)	2 (22.2)	1 (11.1)
AZM (15)	2 (22.2)	4 (44.4)	3 (33.3)

Source: Field data, 2021
Abbreviations: AMC = amoxicillin clavulanic acid, CN = gentamicin, AZM = azithromycin, IMI = imipenem, SXT = Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, CRO = ceftriaxone, CAZ = ceftazidime

Discussion

Upper and lower respiratory tract infections, such as tuberculosis, pneumonia, and systemic mycosis infections, pose a significant health burden on immunocompromised individuals.²⁵ However, the introduction of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) has shown promising results in reducing the incidence of these infections. HAART works by effectively reducing

the viral load of HIV in the pulmonary system and mitigating the associated inflammatory responses.^{9,26} The incidence rate of LRTI in this study was 39.3% which is higher than 13.9% rate reported by Odeyemi *et al.* in a study carried out in Osun state, Nigeria.³ Our rate was however lower than 39.7% and 70.8% rate reported by Ojha *et al.* and Khushbu and Satyam respectively.^{19,27} These variations in incidence rates can be attributed to several factors, including differences

in population characteristics, geographical locations, and healthcare practices. Nonetheless, the findings highlight the substantial prevalence of LRTIs among immunocompromised individuals. LRTI occurrence was only observed in participants with CD4 counts less or equals 500 cells/mm³, though highest in those with CD4 count less than 200 cells/mm³. It was observed that the development of LRTI was significantly associated with lower CD4 cell count. This is in accordance with studies by Odeyemi *et al.*, Ojha *et al.*, and Lamas *et al.*,^{3,19,25} which reported increased CD4 count to have protected against LRTI. The reason for this can be attributed to previously documented findings that increased CD4 cells count aide in controlled and efficient immune response to pathogens whereas decreased CD4 cell counts increases infection (including LRTI) risk in PLWHA. Since CD4 cells are one of HIV's primary targets, its decline is correlated with high viral loads with increased infection risk.²⁸ In line with this, our study observed higher occurrence rate of LRTI in those with viral load greater or equal to 1000 copies/mL and also showed there was a statistical association between LRTI prevalence and viral load. This is in line with previous findings by Crothers *et al.*, Candiani *et al.*, and de Campos *et al.*^{26,29,30} However, although those who achieve viral load suppression aren't at risk of infection as reported by Lamas *et al.*,²⁵ but our study observed 11% LRTI occurrence rate in those with viral load less than 1000 copies/mL. This observation is supported by Crothers *et al.* and Grubb *et al.*,^{26,31} as they reported infectious lung disease occurrence in HIV virally suppressed participants. The reason for this could have been due to setting cut off value for viral load suppression in this study as < 1000 copies/mL compared with other studies with cut off value of <400 copies/mL. HAART has really transformed opportunistic infections in PLWHA from a uniformly fatal risk into manageable risk through its ability to reduce viral load and restore CD4 cells.^{32,33} This could explain the statistically insignificance (p>0.05) between the prevalence of LRTI and socio-demographic factors like sex, occupation, marital status and educational level of participants in this study. This is consistent with reports by Samson *et al.*⁷ that occupation, marital status and educational level are not associated with infection prevalence. However, age was observed to be statistically associated (p<0.05) with LRTI prevalence in participants. This observation supports the notion by Crothers *et al.*²⁶ that age is an important risk factor for many pulmonary diseases among HIV-infected patients.

In this study, about 18.2% of the virally suppressed patients had LRTI and they were found to have CD4

count within 401-500. This was also observed in a study by Ledergerber *et al.*,³⁴ where minority of patients, developed opportunistic infections despite being suppressed virally suppressed. Anglaret *et al.*³⁵ also stated HIV infected individuals, even with high CD4 cell count are still at high risk (though those with CD4 cell count less than 200 cells/mm³ still have the highest risk) of developing both common and opportunistic infections than the general population. Ledergerber *et al.*³⁴ stated that the reason could be that there're disparities in CD4 cell recovery rate as some have slow CD4 cell recovery rate despite suppressed viral load. Also, the reason could be due to behavioral factors being neglected by patient.³⁶

The antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in this study demonstrated that imipenem exhibited the highest effectiveness among the tested antibiotics. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Uzoamaka *et al.*,³⁷ suggesting that imipenem's clinical efficacy may be attributed to its limited use and lower incidence of misuse by patients. Similar research conducted by Mukhopadhyay,³⁸ and Behera *et al.*³⁹ has also reported limited resistance to carbapenems due to their restricted usage. Conversely, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole displayed a high level of resistance against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria in the study. The frequent prescription of trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole to people living with HIV or its potential misuse by these individuals may contribute to the observed resistance. This finding is consistent with a study conducted by Khushbu and Satyam,²⁷ which reported a high resistance rate to cotrimoxazole (trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole) among both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria.

Conclusion

This study has given information on Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (LRTI) among PLWHA on HAART in the study region. We found that infectious and non-infectious pulmonary diseases are substantially increased among PLWHA and our data suggests a clear correlation between LRTI occurrence with CD4 count and viral load of PLWHA irrespective of sex, marital status, occupation or level of education, hitherto an underscore of the importance of factors such as CD4 cell counts, viral load, and age in determining the risk of developing these infections. This study revealed that the routine antibiotic given in the region to PLWHA as prophylaxis is showing high level of resistance which creates alarm for an immediate action for judicious use of antibiotics.

Περίληψη

Bacterial Aetiologic Profile and Antibiotic Response Patterns of Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (LRTI) among HIV/AIDS Patients on Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy (HAART) in Uyo, South-south Nigeria

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Η εξαιρετικά αποτελεσματική αντιρετροϊκή θεραπεία (HAART) μειώνει το ιικό φορτίο του HIV, το οποίο με τη σειρά του αυξάνει τον αριθμό των CD4 και αναμένεται να μειώσει τον κίνδυνο ευκαιριακών λοιμώξεων, όπως η λοίμωξη του κατώτερου αναπνευστικού συστήματος (LRTI). Ως εκ τούτου, η παρούσα μελέτη αξιολόγησε το βακτηριακό αιτιολογικό προφίλ και τα πρότυπα ανταπόκρισής τους στα αντιβιοτικά της λοίμωξης της κατώτερης αναπνευστικής οδού (LRTI) μεταξύ ασθενών με HIV υπό HAART στο Uyo της Νιγηρίας. Αυτή η μελέτη συμπεριέλαβε 61 άτομα που ζούσαν με HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) και ελάμβαναν HAART. Χρησιμοποιήθηκαν τα νοσοκομειακά αρχεία, τυποποιημένα ερωτηματολόγια και συλλέχθηκε από τους συμμετέχοντες δείγμα πτυέλων απαλλαγμένο από σάλιο. Τα δείγματα πτυέλων υποβλήθηκαν σε εργαστηριακή ανάλυση: μικροσκοπική εξέταση, καλλιέργεια και ταυτοποίησης των απομονούμενων παθογόνων. Πραγματοποιήθηκε επίσης έλεγχος ευαισθησίας στα αντιβιοτικά με χρήση συμβατικών βακτηριολογικών μεθόδων. Από τα 61 δείγματα, τα 24 (39,3%) έδωσαν *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Rothia kristinae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus spp*. Ο επιπολασμός των LRTI συσχετίστηκε στατιστικά ($p < 0,05$) με τον αριθμό των CD4, το ιικό φορτίο και την ηλικία, αλλά όχι στατιστικά σημαντικά ($p > 0,05$) με το φύλο, το επάγγελμα, την οικογενειακή κατάσταση και το μορφωτικό επίπεδο του ασθενούς. Τόσο στα Gram-θετικά όσο και στα Gram-αρνητικά παθογόνα, η ιμιπενέμη έδειξε υψηλή ευαισθησία, ενώ η τριμεθοπρίμη-σουλφαμεθοξαζόλη έδειξε υψηλό επίπεδο αντοχής. Η παρούσα μελέτη επιβεβαιώνει ότι ο αυξημένος αριθμός CD4 και το μειωμένο ιικό φορτίο είναι η καλύτερη παρέμβαση για την πρόληψη ευκαιριακών λοιμώξεων, όπως το LRTI σε PLWHA υπό HAART.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

λοιμώξεις του κατώτερου αναπνευστικού συστήματος, αντιρετροϊκή αγωγή, άτομα που ζουν με HIV, CD4, Ιός ανθρώπινης ανοσοανεπάρκειας/Σύνδρομο Επίκτητης Ανοσοανεπάρκειας (HIV/AIDS)

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